

Speculation on the Photon Solution from Maxwell's EM Equations

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The photon solution, following from Maxwell's EM equations, is usually described in terms of E (electric) and B (magnetic) fields satisfying separate wave equations leading to $\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ solutions. E and B fields are perpendicular to each other and to the direction of motion and E and B have the same magnitude. The average energy is w and the average momentum k , using energy density $= .5\epsilon_0 E \cdot E + .5/\mu_0 B \cdot B$ ((1a)) and Poynting momentum density $1/\mu_0 E \times B$ ((1b)). A possible problem in this description is the notion of an average energy and momentum. How is it that the energy is fluctuating in space and the momentum when there is conservation of energy and momentum?

In this note, we try to seek the roots of the photon and argue that it emerges already from $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial ((2)). This form arises from a Lorentz transformation of a point charge with the condition that the E field in the moving frame must depend on the (x,y,z) vector in that frame and not contain $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ (even though the general function multiplying the vector may). We have mentioned this point in a previous note. A point we wish to make is that ((1)) immediately has a nonconstant solution $\phi = f(-\omega t + kx)$, $A = \phi(1,0,0)$ ((3)), with $w/k=c=\text{constant}$, where f is any function, such that $E=0, B=0$. If this solution represents a physical object, then this object has A and ϕ in every frame and cannot represent a charge which may exist in a rest frame, i.e. it is assumed that a charge has some rest mass. ((2)), however, does not seem to represent a physical It seems, however, that if ((3)) is to make physical sense, it should have an energy density and momentum density ((1a,b)). These should be translationally invariant, but ((3)) is not a constant, so a periodic function is the best one can have, but there exist many periodic functions. A basis set for any periodic function is the Fourier series. Moreover, as shown in ((1)), $f(-\omega t + kx) = \cos(-\omega t + kx)$ (or sin) with $A = \phi \{1,1,1\}$ and $\phi = \cos(-\omega t + kt)$ leads to w as average energy and k as average momentum. The average is taken over a cycle in space-time, but conservation of energy and momentum dictates (at least classically) that one cannot have energy and momentum disappearing and reappearing in space-time. This suggests that a different interpretation of the periodicity function is required as suggested in ((1)). It seems that w and k should be the energy and momentum at any x,t , but that $W = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ represents a kind of probability, such that $W(w_1, k_1)W(w_2, k_2) = W(w_1 + w_2, k_1 + k_2)$.

This approach, however, eliminates appearing/disappearing energy, momentum by introducing a two dimensional fluctuating spatial-time density. The two-dimensional feature, however, guarantees conservation of probability in time space because $W^*W=1$ which holds for constant motion.

Thus, we argue that the one requirement that E (electric field) for a point charge depend on the r vector in the moving frame, and not contain g (even though g may appear in a functional form of E), leads to the notion of a quantum wavefunction for a photon solution which is not associated with a charge. This seems to be due to the fact that one has two derivatives: $-\text{grad } \phi$ and $-dA/dt$ partial, for two different variables suggesting that one function of the joint variable $-\omega t + kx$ may yield a zero solution.

Vector Reason for $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial

A point charge in a rest frame is described by $F=qE$ and $E = -\text{grad } \phi$, where q is test charge and $\phi(Q)$ where Q is the source charge. Here “ denotes the rest frame. This description is in agreement with Newtonian mechanics for a conservative force. Given Gauss' law: $\text{grad} \cdot E = \text{charge density}$, the for a point charge:

$$-\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad } \phi = Q \delta(r=0) \quad ((4a)) \text{ so } \phi = Q / \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \quad ((4b))$$

Given that $q\phi$, potential energy is like rest mass, it Lorentz transforms as:

$$(0, q\phi) \rightarrow (qA, q\phi) = (qvg\phi, qg\phi) \quad ((5)) \text{ where } g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$$

Here A is a vector, while ϕ is a scalar. One may ask: What is E as seen from the moving frame? One would still expect a $-\text{grad } \phi$ piece, but $\phi=g\phi$ and one may rewrite x',y',z' in terms of x,y,z in the moving frame, i.e.

$$y'=y, z'=z \text{ and } g(x-vt) = x' \quad ((6))$$

$$-\text{grad } 1/\sqrt{g^2(x-vt)(x-vt) + yy + zz} = e_i g g(x-vt) + e_j y + e_k z / (g^2(x-vt)(x-vt) + yy + zz)^{1.5} \quad ((7)) \text{ } e_i, e_j, e_k \text{ are unit vectors}$$

The problem with ((7)) is that the vector part of the expression depends on $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, but $x-vt, y$ and z are the usual variable for the vector in the moving frame. E is a physical observable and should have a vector portion of $(x-vt) e_i + y e_j + z e_k$, even though this may be multiplied by a function containing g . The question is how does one obtain an extra E piece? This must be a vector. Velocity ϕ will not solve the problem, grad with A does not make a vector except through $\text{grad } xA$ which has a 0 x component because $A = (v\phi, 0, 0)$. Thus, one may try:

$$dA/dt \text{ partial} = v(-v) g g e_i / (g^2(x-vt)(x-vt) + yy + zz)^{1.5} \quad ((8))$$

((8)) combined with ((7)) removes $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, hence:

$$E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt \text{ partial} \quad ((9))$$

Consequences of $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial

We argue that the consequences of $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial ((9)), obtained specifically for a point charge, are major because ((9)) allows a non-constant solution of:

$$f(-wt+kx) = \phi \text{ and } A = \phi(1,0,0) \quad ((10))$$

The problem with ((10)) is that it yields $E=0$ and $B=0$, so there is no energy density or momentum density ((1)). This may, however, be easily remedied by choosing:

$$\phi = f(-\omega t + kx) \text{ and } A = \phi \{1, 1, 1\} \quad ((11))$$

Given that there is a ϕ and A , one requires that there is no rest frame or charge, because a charge having rest mass implies a rest frame.

The question is still: What is f ? Given the notion of translational invariance, one would expect $f(-\omega t + kx)$ to be periodic, the closest behaviour to translational invariance, but there are many periodic functions.

We showed in ((1)) that $\phi = \cos(-\omega t + kx)$ leads to ω as average energy and k as average momentum using ((1)) and integrating over a half period. This, however, begs the question: Why should one take an average to obtain a value ω or k ? By energy and momentum conservation, there is a problem with energy and momentum appearing/disappearing, at least classically.

We suggest that there must be an alternative interpretation of $f(-\omega t + kx)$ which does not violate conservation. Such an interpretation follows if one chooses:

$$f(-\omega t + kx) = \exp(-i\omega t + ikx) \quad ((12)) \text{ for two reasons.}$$

First, if $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ is considered to be an unusual probability, then $W(\omega_1, k_1)W(\omega_2, k_2) = W(\omega_1 + \omega_2, k_1 + k_2)$, i.e. conservation of momentum and energy. The problem of conservation, however, has not been shifted to space-time, but the two vector nature of a complex function solves this issues because: $W^*W = 1$ which is the spatial probability of a constant moving object.

Thus, we argue that:

- (A) One does not really need a wave-equation to find a photon solution (although there is nothing wrong with the wave equation)
- (B) One should really consider $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ as a photon solution and interpret it as an unusual probability, but at least one that does not violate conservation of energy, momentum or spatial probability. It does, however, lead to a complex probability in space which, however, may be used to solve the probability reflection-refraction problem of a single photon.

In other words, we suggest that special relativistic transformation issues with $-\text{grad } \phi$ lead to $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial and this in turn leads to a quantum mechanical unusual probability solution $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ for a photon.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to investigate the root of the photon solution of Maxwell's EM equations. We suggest that one does not need to use wave-equations for E, B in order to see the emergence of the photon, although there is nothing wrong with the wave-equations.

We suggest that the notion of a photon arises from a Lorentz transformation of $(0, \phi''')$, where ϕ''' is the rest frame potential energy of a point charge. In the rest frame, $E''' = -\text{grad}''' \phi'''$,

but this yields a vector portion (x'', y'', z'') which is the usual r "vector. If one uses $-\text{grad } g \text{ phi}$ " in the moving frame, one does not obtain the usual position vector, but rather $(g(x-vt), y, z)$. dA/dt phi is required to remove g . Thus $E = -\text{grad } \text{phi} - dA/dt$ partial. The double term and the two variables, one x in the direction of motion and t immediately lead to a solution $f(-\omega t + kx)$ for $E=0$. If one uses $\text{phi}=f(-\omega t + kx)$ and $A=\text{phi}(1,0,0)$, then $E=B=0$, but phi and $A=\text{phi}\{1,1,1\}$ leads to a solution with energy density and Poynting momentum density.

Respecting translational invariance suggests $f(-\omega t + kx)$ is periodic, but what periodic function should be chosen? Before even choosing a periodic function, however, one may see that there is a conservation issue with a periodic function because it leads to fluctuating energy and momentum density. How does one retain periodicity and conservation? We suggest that one use $W=\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ as an unusual probability. This ensures $W(\omega_1, k_1)W(\omega_2, k_2) = W(\omega_1 + \omega_2, k_1 + k_2)$ and $W^*W=1$, so even spatial probability is conserved. One may still use $E=\cos(-\omega t + kx)$ and integrate the energy density, but one should consider this quantity with caution. There is, however, something unusual happening in that that ω, k object has probability $\exp(-i\omega t + ikx)$ to be at different x, t and this may manifest itself physically in interactions with small objects (\hbar/k). Furthermore, this probability approach may be applied to a single photon probabilistic reflection-refraction problem in one dimension, showing that the probability interpretation is not necessarily far-fetched.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Lorentz Transformation of Photon EM Field Energy and Poynting Momentum and Phase Invariance Physically Defining a Wave Part II (preprint, zenodo, 2024)